

Supplementary table. The 264 articles, divided into the different trends (in alphabetical order per year)

1. Adverse globalization (49)	Abad (2020), Adams et al. (2019), Bartley (2018), Baud & Durand (2012), Borrás et al. (2020), Boussebaa & Faulconbridge (2019), Carminati (2019), Carroll & Klassen (2010), Chu (2001), Delalieux & Moquet (2020), Dios & Cosenza (2019), Etzioni-Halevy (2002), Fodor et al. (2019), French & Wokutch (2005), Froneberg (2007), Greer & Hauptmeier (2016), Harris (2012), Hart-Landsberg (2015), Jensen & McGillivray (2005), Jin (2008), Kim (2015), Kuditchini (2008), Kwon & Pohlmann (2018), Latham & Beaudry (2001), Lauwo et al. (2016), LeBaron (2015), Lee & Lee (2015), Linsi et al. (2021), Liu & Yeung (2008), Luyckx & Janssens (2020), Oliveira (2019), Prasad (2008), Rose-Ackerman (2002), Ruggie (2018), Sabelli (1998), Salt et al. (2000), Sergeev (2020), Sklair (1997, 2002), Sprague (2009), Staples (2008), Steingard & Fitzgibbons (1995), Suleymanov & Valeeva (2018), Tausch & Heshmati (2012), Ulmer (1980), Unterweger (2022), Utting & Zammit (2009), Whelan et al. (2009), Yeganeh (2019)
2. Glocalization (52)	Ailon & Kunda (2009), Appelbaum et al. (2011), Applbaum (2000), Ascani (2018), Assouad & Parboteeah (2018), Bartels & Pavier (1997), Bashan & Armon (2019), Bashan & Kordova (2022), Bashan & Notea (2018), Belis-Bergouignan et al. (2000), Beret et al. (2003), Buckley & Casson (2009), Cannon & Yaprak (2011), Chuang et al. (2011), Czinkota & Ronkainen (2009), de Rijke & Plucker (2011), Foss (2007), Fukukawa & Teramoto (2009), Geary & Roche (2001), Gertsen & Soderberg (2010), Gerybadze & Merk (2014), Giulianotti & Robertson (2004), Gjolberg (2009), Gulbro & Herbig (1999), Hana et al. (2020), Harvey et al. (2008), Hegde & Hicks (2008), Heley et al. (2020), Javernick-Will & Scott (2010), Jones (2007), Lane (1998), Lau et al. (1996), Li (2019), Malnight (1995), McDonnell et al. (2014), Millar & Choi (2010), Mtar (2010), Munjal et al. (2018), Murray et al. (2010), Palazzo (2002), Poster (2008), Reddy & Sigurdson (1997), Rugman & Verbeke (2008), Schmalz et al. (2021), Schneider (2009), Selmer & Lam (2004), Shenkar (2004), Slater et al. (2007), Thompson & Kaspersen (2012), Vahlne & Jonsson (2017), Wan et al. (2003), Wrigley et al. (2005)
3. Hyperglobalization (67)	Agmon (2003), Ali & Camp (1996), Aluko et al. (2021), Applbaum (1999), Ashton et al. (2010), Asmussen et al. (2007), Aspelund et al. (2007), Athukorala & Kohpaiboon (2010), Barjot (2011), Beaverstock & Boardwell (2000), Boussebaa (2021), Buckley (2009), Coucke & Sleuwaegen (2008), Crick (2009), Detomasi (2007), Devinney (2011), Dingwerth & Pattberg (2009), Eberlein et al. (2014), Elias (2008), Elias & Beasley (2009), Fortanier et al. (2020), Fraiberg (2017), Gabrielsson et al. (2016), Gannon et al. (2014), Gerybadze & Reger (1999), Guo & D'Ambra (2009), Hall (2015), Hua et al. (2022), Hurta et al. (2018), Jones (2005, 2011), Kapoor & Sherif (2012), Kauppinen (2012), Laanti et al. (2007), Leffel et al. (2022), Liu & Uzunidis (2021), Luterbacher et al. (2017), Macdonald & Macdonald (2017), May (2017), McCann & Acs (2011), Meckling (2011), Narula & Hagedoorn (1999), Niforou (2014), O'Donnell & Jeong (2000), Pritchard (1998), Puente (2020), Pyle & Ward (2003), Reilly & Scott (2014), Robbins (2004), Rosenblatt (2011), Rotter et al. (2014), Ryan et al. (2022), Scherer et al. (2006), Sleuwaegen & Onkelinx (2014), Staples (2007), Tallman & Koza (2010), Thrall (2021), Tozanli (1998), Vahlne et al. (2018), Vahlne & Ivarsson (2014), Weiss & Wilkinson (2022), Whelan (2012), Wilkins (2009), Wills (1998), Winder (2006), Wirtz et al. (2015), Wright & Nancarrow (1999)
4. Global development (32)	Aldashev & Verdier (2009), Amoroso & Moncada-Paterno-Castello (2018), Arnold (2003), Bae et al. (2003), Boon (2017), Bu & Liu (2022), Buckley (2006), Cantwell & Janne (2000), Czinkota & Ronkainen (2005), Detomasi (2015), Dogan (2010), Dunning (1994), Faulconbridge & Muzio (2015), Fraticiu (2019), Head & Ries (2002), Iguchi (2012), Jones (2008), Kant (2016), Khan (1986), Krueger (2008), Lee & Kim (2010), Levy (2007), Lozano & Boni (2002), Mosley & Uno (2007), Mukherjee (2018), Neumayer & De Soysa (2005),

	Reddy (1997), Root (1984), Rugman (2010), Schuh (2007), Tomohara & Takii (2011), Yamashita & Fukao (2010)
5. New globalization (64)	Aguiar & Micussi (2022), Alon et al. (2011), Arregle et al. (2016), Athukorala (2017), Autio et al. (2021), Avioutsikii & Tensaout (2020), Berrill & Hovey (2018), D. Black & O’Bright (2016), J. Black & Morrison (2012), Buckley (2019), Buckley & Casson (2021), Buckley & Hashai (2014, 2020), Bull & Miklian (2019), Butzbach et al. (2020), Calabro et al. (2022), Callaghan (2021), Cheng et al. (2011, 2012), Choy et al. (2010), Contractor (2022), Cooke (2012), Cooke et al. (2019), Dahan et al. (2021), de la Torre et al. (2011), Eckhardt et al. (2017), Evsuykov (2021), Fang et al. (2017), Gavrilko & Pobochenko (2021), Grosse et al. (2021), Guedhami et al. (2022), Han et al. (2018), Hitt et al. (2016), Hooper & Holtbrugge (2020), Iqbal et al. (2018), Johns et al. (2019), Kahler (2018), Klein & Wocke (2007), Kobrin (2017), Lee et al. (2017), Lee & Eckhardt (2017), Luo (2022), Luo & Witt (2022), Macdonald & Macdonald (2020), MacKenzie, Eckhardt, et al. (2017), MacKenzie, Ross, et al. (2017), Meyer (2017), Nayir & Vaiman (2012), Ozawa (2018), Pal & Buzzanell (2013), Pedersen (2008), Peretz & Morley (2021), Petricevic & Teece (2019), Pillania (2008), Prashantham et al. (2018), Sharma et al. (2020), Sun (2010), Teece (2022), Thangavel et al. (2022), Toporowski (2010), Verbeek & Mah (2020), Wang et al. (2014), Whipple et al. (2009), Witt (2019)

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